

Climateurope2

Community Engagement Strategy

Deliverable 6.1

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About Climateurope2

Timely delivery and effective use of climate information is fundamental for a green recovery and a resilient, climate-neutral Europe, in response to climate change and variability. Climate services address this through the provision of climate information for use in decision-making to manage risks and realise opportunities.

The market and need for climate information have seen impressive progress in recent years and are expected to grow in the foreseeable future. However, the communities involved in the development and provision of climate services are often unaware of each other and lack interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary knowledge. In addition, quality assurance, relevant standards, and other forms of assurance (such as guidelines, and good practices) for climate services are lagging behind. These are needed to ensure the saliency, credibility, legitimacy, and authoritativeness of climate services, and build two-way trust between supply and demand.

Climateurope2 aims to develop future equitable and quality-assured climate services to all sectors of society by:

- Developing standardisation procedures for climate services
- Supporting an equitable European climate services community
- Enhancing the uptake of quality-assured climate services to support adaptation and mitigation to climate change and variability

The project will identify the support and standardisation needs of climate services, including criteria for certification and labelling, as well as the user-driven criteria needed to support climate action. This information will be used to propose a taxonomy of climate services, suggest community-based good practices and guidelines, and propose standards where possible. A large variety of activities to support the communities involved in European climate services will also be organised.

Executive Summary

The aim of WP6 is to promote an open exchange of knowledge, expertise and data among the climate services community. The climate services community is defined as the network of organisations and people who contribute to providing and using climate services. Task 6.1 identifies gaps in the diversity of the participants of the European climate service network. This document D6.1 develops a strategy to improve the representation of different kinds of stakeholders from public and private sectors, reach a greater inclusion from under-represented regions (e.g. Eastern Europe) and enhance the attainment of gender balance across the network. The community engagement strategy is a concise live document and it will be updated twice in order to monitor network evolution and engagement, and to adjust the strategy to reach low-represented and highly-relevant communities.

Between 2016 and 2021, the Climateurope project built up a diverse network of individuals and organisations in the field of CS and Earth system modelling from across different sectors; academia, NGOs, private business, governments, and the general public. In the final year, Climateurope had created a network of 388 members. The members of the Climateurope network were asked individually if they agreed to sharing their contact information with the new project and joining the Climateurope2 community. Several methods for engagement of the community are inherited from Climateurope (social media, Festivals and Webstivals, webinars, etc.).

The strategy uses two main ways to organise interaction: communication channels and events. Regarding the channels, three types are used for interaction:

- The Climateurope2 project website is a public medium to inform anyone interested in the aims, progress, activities and results of the Climateurope2 project and where the climate services community can share information about other relevant initiatives.
- A Climateurope2 Platform, will be created where the Climateurope2 network members can engage with other people working with climate services, participate in discussions about good practices, guidelines, find useful resources for climate change adaptation and mitigation, and access the most relevant results of the project.
- Social media channels, such as LinkedIn and Twitter will be used in the project to engage with several audiences, and also the Climateurope2 network.

Several types of events will be organised for interaction with the network to share knowledge, opinions, experiences and to widen the network:

- A webinar series with stakeholders' perspectives, which will be of interest for different audiences, including the private sector
- Invited webinars from other projects and initiatives
- Webstivals and Festivals
- A Roadshow visiting different countries across South East Europe
- Business breakfasts targeting standardisation and certification institutions and other business stakeholders.
- Sessions and side events in other conferences such as ECCA, EGU and EMS

- Sessions and side events in selected business arenas and conferences; the private sector needs specific engagement activities, also through intermediaries

Next to exploiting the communication channels and events, WP6 will organise interaction with sister projects to widen and strengthen the network of climate services as well as the relations with interested institutions, to explore chances for further exploitation of project outcomes. WP6 assists with creating connections between WPs 1-5 and the climate services community. The community is critical for understanding standardisation needs and is therefore needed for providing information to key deliverables in, for example, WP1. All WPs will also have direct contacts with members of the climate services community, and these interactions are expected to grow as the project progresses. WP6 offers expertise and support for new and/or better interaction. A discussion with WPs 1-5 will be organised to define specific aims and targets.

Finally, a monitoring tool will be developed for tracking the network's diversity, equity and inclusiveness. Aspects to be monitored are regional gaps (e.g. in terms of EU Member States or European countries), gender balance, age (e.g. youth engagement), and gaps in sectors or organisation types.

Keywords

Climate services community, Climateurope2 network, engagement strategy, events, platform, social media, diversity, equity and inclusiveness

1 Introduction

Consultancy companies and government organisations offer climate services so that users can manage climate change risks and exploit the opportunities of a changing climate. Climate services (CS) have undergone major development in recent years and are expected to grow rapidly due to the urgency in planning for adaptation and managing climate risks more effectively. However, it is sometimes questionable whether the knowledge, tools and advice provided can withstand a test of scientific quality or demonstrate that they are fit for purpose and salient for user's needs. Quality assurance methods, technical standards, guidelines and good practices for climate services exist (e.g. [the WMO standards and guidelines](#)), but they are not widely known outside of the network of the National Hydro-Meteorological Services (NHMSs). In addition, these existing standards are incomplete, only touching on a few components of climate services as they do not address the full value chain of climate services. The field remains dominated by scientists whose tools and platforms are often quite inaccessible to the average user. Thus, a major effort to understand the requirements for a minimum benchmark of quality and effectiveness of climate services is urgent. Climateurope2 aims to support the development of accessible, effective and climate services and to identify what should be the threshold of their minimum quality in an equitable manner for all sectors of society by:

- Developing standardisation procedures for climate services;
- Building a fair European network for climate services;
- Improving climate services to support adaptation to and mitigation of climate change and climate variability.

This document (Deliverable D6.1) describes the Community Engagement Strategy of the Horizon Europe project Climateurope2. It describes the status of the Climateurope2 network at the start of the project and a strategy to further develop this network to include a larger part of the climate services community. A publishable version of this deliverable will be available in M9 (May 2023). This strategy will then become a live document that is evaluated and updated twice during the project (D6.2, D6.3). For an overview of WP6 deliverables, see Annex 1.

Climateurope2 network: everyone who is actively involved in the Climateurope2 project.

Climate services community: everyone involved with climate services as producer or user, partly involved in the Climateurope2 network and partly not yet involved.

Neither the community nor the network are static entities. The climate services community will grow autonomously. As Climateurope2 team we aim to enhance this growth by bringing the actors needed for standardising and for improving the quality of climate services into the community. We also aim to grow the Climateurope2 network of active participants.

This strategy will contribute to one of the aims of Climateurope2, namely on strengthening the climate services community. This can be realised by providing live and online platforms where climate service providers can interact with each other as well as with users. Community engagement is also instrumental for the project itself, because we need to build consensus on quality requirements,

common procedures and standardisation of climate services. The aim of WP6 is to promote an open exchange of knowledge, expertise and data among the climate services community to identify:

- Existing standards and remaining gaps in standardisation;
- Usable and effective labelling and certification;
- Good practices in climate services ;
- Economic, social and environmental values of using climate services;
- Current market of CS, its gaps and possible future developments;
- Decision making and policy support requirements.

WP6 will also promote networking and exchange within the community, support market development and assist other work packages in their exchanges with the climate services community.

1.1 Aims of this strategy

The aims of this community engagement strategy (from Grant Agreement part A):

- Establish, further develop and monitor the Climateurope2 network;
- Identify gaps in the diversity of the participants of this European climate service network
- Improve the representation of different stakeholder typologies from public and private sectors;
- Reach a greater inclusion from under-represented regions (e.g. Eastern Europe);
- Enhance the attainment of a diverse and inclusive community.
- Actively engage community members in the activities of the Climateurope2 project
- Bring the community together, enhance knowledge exchange between community members, and build links across the climate services value chain.
- Connect the Climateurope2 network to participatory processes in the project WPs, doing it in a structured and optimised way.

1.2 Who represent the community?

The climate services community is defined as the network of organisations and people who contribute to providing and using climate services. This includes organisations and individuals in the 'production chain' such as, producers of climate data (producers of data, climate modellers, data analysts), software producers and so on. Users of climate services are also included in the community. The community may include academia, government, businesses, industry, NGOs, and citizens' associations. A first climate services network was already developed in the former Climateurope project, and the aim now is to expand this network to include other climate service actors, with focus on inclusion of underrepresented groups (Figure 1). In principle, the whole climate services community, including potential users of climate services, is the target group of this engagement strategy.

Figure 1. Different stakeholder groups involved or targeted in the Climateurope2 project

2 Overall approach

Using Figure 1 as a visualisation, the aim of the engagement strategy is to expand the network across the circles. The inner circle corresponds to the consortium, and then external engagement already starts with a climate services network inherited from Climateurope. In Climateurope2 we want to expand this initial network by including new members from the third and fourth circles.

Figure 2 depicts the structure of the strategy regarding engagement of the community. On the left side are the Climateurope2 work packages and on the right side the external members of the climate services community. In the middle are the two main ways to organise interaction: communication channels and events. WP6 and WP7 will cooperate to organise this interaction during the project lifetime. WP6 also monitors the interaction and the network (including gaps) and proposes options for improvement.

Figure 2. Visualisation of the community engagement strategy. On the right side, the members and potential new members of the community. In the middle, the different actions to engage existing and new members, including monitoring of growing membership and diversity of the community. On the left, the work packages that contribute to and benefit from engaging with the community members. The arrows show an iterative process.

3 Current status of the Climateurope2 network

Between 2016 and 2021, the Climateurope project built up a diverse network of individuals and organisations in the field of climate services and Earth system modelling from across different sectors; academia, NGOs, private business, governments, and the public. In the final year, Climateurope had created a network of 388 members. Figure 3 shows the breakdown of the Climateurope community by organisation type, illustrating the variety of the network. A fifth of the network identified themselves as climate service users from the private sector. No data are available on company size in the private sector.

Figure 3. Breakdown of registered Climateurope network members by type of organisation.

The network provided a resource for knowledge sharing for climate service users and providers across Europe, and to some extent, beyond. Figure 4 shows the worldwide reach of the Climateurope project with network members joining from as far afield as Australia.

Regarding the gender of the Climateurope network, an approximate gender split of 45% : 55% (Female : Male) was achieved. For the LinkedIn network an even gender split 51% : 49% (Female : Male) was achieved.

Figure 4. Climateurope network density map showing the worldwide location of network members

At the end of Climateurope, the recommendations for continuation of the climate services network were:

1. Continue to hold online Webstivals, which remotely bring together the climate science for service communities in an engaging and interactive way.
2. Maintain the Climateurope website, which contains useful climate science for service content.
3. Coordinate a regular Climateurope event at one of the major conferences e.g., European Meteorological Society (EMS), International Conference on Climate Services (ICCS), European Climate Change and Adaptation Conference (ECCA). This could be a run as a special session or a networking event.
4. Maintain the Climateurope LinkedIn account through volunteer moderators.

Several methods for engagement of the community are inherited from Climateurope (social media, Festivals and Webstivals, webinars, etc.).

It is important that while going forward with Climateurope2 the connection with former users of Climateurope is nurtured. The network of Climateurope has been invited to join the Climateurope2 network in a GDPR proof manner. This means that the members of the Climateurope network were asked individually if they agreed to sharing their contact information with the new project and joining the Climateurope2 community. The owner of the personal data in Climateurope (Met Office) contacted the network members informing that the Climateurope project was over, and if they were interested in being part of the new network, they could register (a link to the registration form was provided). The 388 members were invited to join the new Climateurope2 network, and by May 2023, 134 of them did so. Members from the former network that gave informed consent thus became members of the new network voluntarily and actively.

A growing, active climate services network is key for achieving the main objectives of the Climateurope2 project, and developing the climate service network across Europe is a main objective of WP6. Climateurope2 is by definition going to amplify the community as standardisation brings new actors to the table of the climate services community. This is the case not only for standardisation organisations but also others such as organisations that provide guidance to companies in reporting climate change risk, like the TCFD¹. Also, the specific focus on standardisation of CE2 should reach out to those who are not using climate services yet but for whom quality assurance and a better fit-for-purpose would make climate services attractive. WP6 will assist in further development of the network by organizing events, contributing to channels, interacting with other WPs and interacting with other projects, as will be explained in the next chapters.

¹ Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures: <https://www.fsb-tcfd.org/>

4 Channels for engagement

This chapter explains the role of the project website, the interactive Platform, and social media in engaging existing and new community members in Climateurope2. The media are owned by WP7 and WP6 will make active use of them.

4.1 Climateurope2 project website

The project website is a public medium to inform anyone interested in the aims, progress, activities and results of the Climateurope2 project. It can also be a starting point for new members of the climate services community to get connected. The Climateurope website has a banner that directs visitors - if they wish - to the Climateurope2 new website. There are also a couple of places on the Climateurope2 website that link to the former Climateurope website (in 'About the project' and 'Projects and initiatives').

Creating and managing the project website is a task of WP7 (Task 7.1); however, other WPs and external actors and initiatives provide content for the website. The climate services community can share information about other relevant initiatives. For WP6 this means we will provide ideas to enhance the interactive options that this website offers to the climate services community, and help to manage the interaction that results from it.

Present options for interaction and connectivity through the website:

- The homepage has a button for joining the network. This creates a list of members who can be invited to meetings and receive updates about the progress of the project. The form that people should fill out to join the network informs them that “Climateurope2 will use the information you provide in this form to be in touch with you to provide updates on the project’s developments and activities.” BSC will own and manage the resulting list of personal contact data.
- The project will produce a newsletter, and people who are interested can subscribe to this. The homepage has a button for subscribing to this newsletter. In principle, joining the network and subscribing to the newsletter are two different needs that will be managed separately.
- The website has a contact page with a form where visitors can ask questions or send comments to the project team. It also shows an email address allowing visitors to contact the project team directly (infoclimateurope2@bsc.es). These emails are received by BSC staff. The plan is to create a document where the requests are stored so WP6 and WP7 members can analyse the nature of the questions over time (see also the chapter on monitoring).
- Google analytics is active for the website; WP7 will monitor the Google analytics, since visits to the website are one of the KPIs.
- The website has a section of future events that, apart from events internally organised by the project, also includes a section for ‘other climate services events’. This section advertises relevant events from other projects and initiatives and directs the visitor to their websites. The idea of having such a section is that the website is also a hub for the climate services community to know what are the upcoming events of interest for them.

- A section to be deployed soon on the website is a blog. The first post will be written by the Climateurope2 coordinator to give his perspective on the need for standards in climate services. Subsequent posts will give voice to other actors from the climate services community (both internal and external to the project) to share their perspectives and views about a range of topics related to climate change adaptation and mitigation.

4.2 Climateurope2 Platform

WP7 Task 7.4 creates a Climateurope2 Platform, accessible only for members of the Climateurope2 network. See Figure 5 for an overview of the communication vectors in the project, and the position of the platform in this overview. Upon registration to be part of the Climateurope2 network, members will be provided, among other benefits, with the option to use this tool to engage with other people working on climate services, participate in discussions about good practices and guidelines, and explore useful resources for climate change adaptation and mitigation. Network members will be able to use the platform to look for relevant documents related to climate services and standardisation and to visualise other climate services-related information.

A beta version of the platform is planned to be ready in M18; this version will allow for a search of project results and other relevant documents as well as community engagement. There will be additional releases until there is a stable version in M36. The final platform will be ready in M36. To sustain the exploitation of the platform, an API will be developed, so it can be integrated in other platforms after the end of the project.

Figure 5. Communication vectors that will be used in Climateurope2

The platform will also be a science-society interface where the different work packages can interact with stakeholders. The idea is to use the platform for any type of discussion on good practices,

guidelines, and other relevant climate services' issues that require participation from the network. Preliminary results of the project will be shared and feedback from the network collected and discussed to reach consensus. For specific products, parts of the network will become aware of ongoing discussions to acquire sufficient feedback on the drafts. The platform is mentioned explicitly in the work plan of several work packages (see Table 1). That list is not limitative because the Platform will be open for any other interactive use by the work packages. A dialogue with WPs 1-5 is needed to fully use the potential of this platform.

Table 1. Planned use of the Climateurope2 Platform

Work package	Platform use planned
WP1	Inclusion of the synthesis report (the ongoing synthesis of all WPs which includes 3 milestones prior to the final deliverable in month 52).
WP2	Sharing a preliminary version of best practices and current state-of-the-art in the second stage of each task (half way to the project).
WP3	A review of deliverable D3.3 through the platform in the third year. Discuss lessons learnt for the final deliverable D3.4.
WP4	Publish the state of the market on the platform three times (M14 (D4.2) and two updates in M28 (D4.5) and M48 (D4.10)). Share outputs of Task 4.4.

4.3 Social media

Social media are used in the project to engage with several audiences, which also includes the Climateurope2 network. In WP6 we focus on the Climateurope2 network. The usefulness of social media platforms for interactive functions is mainly to create engagement and acquire new network members through the promotion of the project itself, its outputs, and the activities that are organised.

Climateurope developed communities on LinkedIn and Twitter. The LinkedIn account was specifically mentioned as a valuable legacy for Climateurope2. Maintenance of the LinkedIn and Twitter accounts is part of Task 7.1. Twitter and LinkedIn are mainly populated by active individuals, who can often be champions in their field and may have a large network that is not yet involved in Climateurope2. Asking members connected to our LinkedIn account to advertise Climateurope2 and its specific activities (webinars, prototypes, surveys etc) helps increase the project reach and interact with a broader audience. We could offer mutual advertisement to important stakeholders and projects. We might also reach out to influential climate change activists and have them in the network too, since they probably do have a large network and valuable contacts. See for example:

<https://www.influencerintelligence.com/blog/9G/10-climate-change-activists-you-should-follow>.

It is still a question if the social media accounts of Climateurope2 will be expanded to other platforms. For instance, It might be advantageous to use Facebook when advertising webinars and Webstivals when we want the broader public to engage. Before creating a new social media channel we should raise an internal question among members of the consortium about what message/information we want to share and what the target group is (for example, young generations). This final decision related to the choice of communication channels is on WP7. Social media platforms can sometimes rise and fall pretty fast, so an evaluation of their functionality half way through the project seems wise.

It may be useful to attach labels to members in order to create lists of 'stakeholder types' on social media. The labels might be associated with specific storytelling and tailored narratives. Also, specific media may attract different stakeholder types (for example, LinkedIn appeals more to the business community). This way we can better engage with particular groups. This needs to be coordinated with WP7.

5 Events for engagement

5.1 Stakeholders' perspectives webinar series

A webinar series is planned to grow the network and to keep it active and alive. The aim of the webinars is to gather the perspectives, requirements and needs of the climate services community regarding good practices, guidelines and standards for climate services. We can also test how the project (preliminary) results can be useful for them.

Organising a series of webinars is part of Task 6.2, led by CMCC. However, all partners and work packages are expected to propose content for the webinars. Webinars will focus on interaction with stakeholders, so we can better understand their needs and positions. The webinars will be stakeholder targeted including salient topics and narratives which will be of interest for different audiences, including the private sector. At least 6 webinars will be organised in total, starting from year 2. The webinars will be recorded, and presentations and videos will be shared on the project website. Upon registration, participants are informed that the webinar will be recorded and uploaded to the project website and they need to agree with it (this to take care of GDPR guidelines).

5.2 Invited webinars

Together with WP7, invited webinars will be organised presenting other projects and initiatives. External parties such as sister projects, ESA, ECMWF, etc. (outside the consortium but inside the community) are invited to provide content for these webinars. The aims are to gather input on what else is happening in the field of climate services and to increase engagement with the climate services and the standards communities. Partner DNV will be contacted for connecting to the standardisation related organisations. Occasionally, more general topics will be also invited for a webinar (e.g. Foresight Dialogues, understood as a dialog between a climate scientist and an artist).

5.3 Webstivals and Festivals

A Webstival is an online form of a Festival, invented in the Climateurope project due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The online format proved highly successful, because many more people were able to attend the events than would have been possible in-person, and from a much wider geographical range, helping to grow the Climateurope network and its diversity. Furthermore, since held online, Webstivals also contribute to a reduced carbon footprint. Therefore, the recommendation was to continue with this format in Climateurope2.

Through hosting and facilitating both Festivals and Webstivals, Climateurope2 will use innovative approaches to address and engage stakeholders. The aim is to share knowledge, opinions, experiences and to widen the network. Furthermore, we aim to include a diversity of scientific and non-scientific organisations and individuals in the network, such as businesses, funding organisations and SMEs. The content presented can be case studies, climate service products, and prototypes of guidelines and standards produced in Climateurope2, tailored to the needs of stakeholders and with salient topics and narratives to the selected audiences. Typically, during a Climateurope2 Festival and Webstival,

science is integrated with social media channels, arts, music and culture. Webstivals are also a venue where we invite specific communities, for example, industry sector meetings with high vulnerability to climate impacts. When possible, the organisation of Festivals will make use of large climate adaptation events (e.g. the ECCA conference) to take advantage of the climate services community attending these events. CMCC will be the partner from Climateurope2 to oversee the organisation of Webstivals and Festivals.

The plan is to organise:

- Six Webstivals (M6, M12, M24, M31, M45, M52).
- Two in-person Festivals in M18 (Venice) and M38 (Belgrade).

The content for these events can come from inside the project, but content from outside sources such as other European funded projects and organisations will be favoured. A list of projects and initiatives whose members could be potential participants of the network has been compiled by the consortium, and will be used in the future to expand the Climateurope2 network. Registered participants can be involved as speakers or participants in Webstivals later on.

Participation from all WPs is expected in the preparation of content for the Webstivals. Thus, in support of the internal process, a survey will be shared with all partners and work packages of the project to collect the ideas about the format, duration, and content of the Webstivals. Alongside the survey, WP6 members will actively approach all work packages to discuss potential content for the events. The climate services community will also be invited to provide content for certain events. Based on this input, WP6 will create each program and take care of the organisation of the event in collaboration with WP7 and other WPs (who can become co-organizer of a Webstival). Each program in its final draft phase will be proposed as an item on the agenda of the work package leaders meetings.

After the first Webstival, a guideline document with a detailed plan for the organisation of online events has been developed to reflect on the lessons learned and increase the efficiency of the organisation of the next events. An evaluation survey will be sent to participants after each Webstival and Festival to collect their feedback.

5.4 Roadshow

A roadshow is a series of smaller events happening in different countries across South East Europe (SEE). Its aim is to promote the Climateurope2 network in the region of SEE, through local stakeholder engagement in their native language. Ten locations will be selected that were underrepresented in the Climateurope network.

Climateurope2 WP7 will organise capacity building about standards and processes in climate services with assistance from WP1 and WP4. WP6 will offer spaces in the Roadshow to promote the use of the project's materials (for example, on the standards building process) and supports local actors in the organisation of their own events. Roadshows are an opportunity to gather feedback on the needs of the climate services community (for example, standardisation needs, requirements and concerns). The roadshow can also be a way to engage the user community.

The roadshow will take place from M10-M48. We intend to organise the roadshow with present partners in the Climateurope2 (including Serbia (CPN)) as well as local partners from previous projects. We will engage with Copernicus Fora and local knowledge networks, speaking the local languages, who may assist in exporting the outcomes of the project.

5.5 Business breakfasts

Two business breakfasts will target standardisation and certification institutions and other business stakeholders. These events, organised by DNV, will be an opportunity to engage key members of standardisation and certification institutions with the Climateurope2 project, give visibility to its key results and raise awareness on the market potential for certification in the field of climate services for climate change adaptation and mitigation. These meetings will be organized once the project has a minimum level of matured results and insights as well as a targets and salient narrative particularly crafted for the business community.

5.6 Sessions and side events in other conferences

European conferences covering topics like climate change and climate adaptation are potentially interesting venues for engaging new audiences. Some relevant scientific conferences are listed in Table 2. To this list we will add sectoral conferences aimed at growing the network and reaching new audiences, such as the food sector in Europe. We will aim for sessions and side events in selected business arenas and conferences; the private sector needs specific engagement activities, also through intermediaries.

The balance between costs and benefits of a contribution to these conferences must be considered carefully. For example, an oral presentation in a session at a conference may bring 10-15 minutes of contact with a small audience (20-50 people) while it takes 3-4 days of travel and presence at the conference. Material costs include travel, hotel, and a conference fee. Online presentations already are more efficient, although they might be less effective for network building. If a whole session is acquired and can be used entirely to present a draft product and gather feedback, that is more interesting from the viewpoint of WP6. In some cases, arrangements may be made for a side-event during a conference. From the viewpoint of dissemination (WP7) conferences may be a good way to make the climate services community aware of the Climateurope2 project. Especially at the end of the Climateurope2 project final results should be presented.

We take a restricted approach to conferences from the perspective of really being able to engage audiences in an efficient way. We aim to visit 1 conference per year that has an average of minimal 300 participants and is focused on climate change topics. Climateurope2 will participate in the organisation of two of the themes of ECCA 2023: <https://climateurope2.eu/news-events/events/events/ecca2023>. If someone from the consortium travels to a conference for another reason, that can also be an opportunity to submit one additional abstract and present something from the Climateurope2 project.

Table 2. Conferences with relevance for the Climateurope2 network

Acronym	Full title	Schedule	Audience
ECCA	European Conference on Climate Change Adaptation	Every 2 years, 2023	Scientific and non-scientific climate adaptation community
EGU	European Geosciences Union	Yearly in April (Vienna)	Scientists in in the Earth, planetary and space sciences
EMS	European Meteorological Society	Yearly in September (2023 in Bratislava)	Meteorological, climatological and related communities
ICRC-CORDEX	International Conference on Regional Climate - Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment	25-29 of September 2023 in Trieste, Italy	Researchers worldwide in climate data downscaling efforts
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change	Yearly COP meetings (30 November to 12 December 2023 in Dubai) or side events listed here: https://unfccc.int/calendar/events-list	Governments, NGO's and business associations

6 Interaction with other projects

Some projects are explicitly mentioned in the grant agreement because several work packages need to be built on them (see Table 3). The WP6 may connect to these efforts to widen and strengthen the network of climate services.

A list of sister projects, which includes projects funded by the EC DG RTD and some projects for the implementation of the Mission on Climate Adaptation, was drafted. Through personal contacts and official emails, project members were invited to join the community and have bi-lateral meetings with the Climateurope2 coordination team. A close collaboration between sister projects and Climateurope2 is expected to exploit synergies.

Besides this, the consortium was invited to populate a longer list of relevant sister projects and initiatives, whose members can be invited to join the network (Table 4). In this case, a variable level of engagement is expected, from just being informed about the project’s activities to participating with different levels of involvement in activities/events. In the list of projects mainly projects from Horizon 2020 and Europe are listed. We should explore other financial programs as well. There is also EU supporting action INTERREG which finance projects that are more locally and regionally oriented.

Table 3. Relevant projects from the Grant Agreement

Work package	Projects and programs	Audiences
WP1	Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD)	Financial sector
	Standardisation organisations	Business community
WP2	IPCC AR6 and DDC	Researchers in climate change, adaptation and mitigation, policy makers and stakeholders
	ESA CCI - European Space Agency - Climate Change Initiative	Climate data producers
	IS-ENES3 - Infrastructure for the European Network for Earth System Modelling	Climate modellers, climate data producers and climate data users
	RDA - Research Data Alliance	Owners of climate data
WP4	MARCO - Market Research for a Climate services Observatory	Climate service providers

	EU-MACS - EUropean MArket for Climate Services	Climate service providers and users
	European Research Programs including the EU Mission on Climate Adaptation and Societal Transformation	Wide range of researchers and research users
	Climate-KIC	Climate service providers
	Copernicus C3S	Climate service providers
	JPI Climate	Climate, adaptation and mitigation researchers
	WMO - World Meteorological Organisation	Meteorologists, climate scientists
	GFDRR - Global Facility for Disaster Reduction and Recovery (World Bank)	Climate service users
WP5	ERA4CS	Climate data users, adaptation and mitigation researchers
WP6	CSP - Climate Services Partnership	Climate service providers
	GFCS - Global Framework for Climate Services (WMO)	Governments and organisations that produce and use climate information and services
WP8	EOSC- European Open Science Cloud	Climate data producers and data users
	HORIZON-CL3-2022-DRS-01-03 Horizon Topic Improved quality assurance / quality control of data used in decision-making related to risk management of natural hazards, accidents and CBRN events	Climate service providers
	HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01-21 Horizon Topic Leveraging standardisation in Digital Technologies (CSA)	Standardisation community
	HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-18 Horizon Topic Fostering standardisation to boost European industry's competitiveness (CSA)	Standardisation community

	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-13 Horizon Topic Strengthening Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research communities in climate, energy and mobility disciplines	Climate service users
	HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-01-01 Horizon Topic Better prepared regional and local authorities to adapt to climate change	Climate service users
	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-03 Horizon Topic Maximising the impact and synergy of European climate change research and innovation	Climate service providers and users

Table 4. Sister projects

Acronym	Full name and description	URL	Project coordination	Funding	End date
MAGICA	Maximising the synergy of European research governance and innovation for climate action	[no project website, but use this:] https://jpi-climate.eu/programme/magica/	Basque Centre for Climate Change (BC3). Project coordinator: María José Sanz mj.sanz@bc3research.org	Horizon 2020	5/31/26
MAIA	Maximising impact and accessibility of european climate research	[no website yet, use]	Fondazione Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC) Project coordinator: Dr Giulia Galluccio, giulia.galluccio@cmcc.it	Horizon 2020	8/31/25
I-CHANGE	Individual change of habits needed for green	https://ichange-project.eu/	Centro Internazionale in Monitoraggio	Horizon 2020	4/30/25

	European transition		Ambientale - Fondazione CIMA info@ichange-project.eu		
HARMONIA	Support system for improved resilience and sustainable urban areas	http://harmonia-project.eu/	Politecnico di Milano Project coordinator: Julia Tzortzi julia.georgi@polimi.it	Horizon 2020	1/31/25
SOCIO-BEE	Wearables and drones for city socio-environmental observations and behavioural change	https://socio-bee.eu/	Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis Project coordinator: Evangelos V. Kopsachellis ekops@iti.gr	Horizon 2020	30/11/2024
COMPAIR	Compair Community Observation Measurement & Participation in AIR Science	https://www.wecompair.eu/	Digital Vlaanderen (Digital Flanders) (BE) digitaal.vlaanderen@vlaanderen.be	Horizon 2020	31/10/2024
EIFFEL	Earth Observation applications for climate change adaptation and mitigation	https://www.eiffel4climate.eu/	Institute of Communication and computer Systems	Horizon 2020	5/31/24
PROTECT	Procuring innovative climate change services	not available yet, we could add the cordis link https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060592	Marc Pattinson mpattinson@group-gac.com	Horizon 2020	5/1/24

ECFAS	European coastal flood awareness system	https://www.ecfas.eu/	Istituto Universitario di Studi Superiori di Pavia (IUSS), Italy Project coordinator: Ruth Higgins (Dr.) ecfas.project@gmail.com	Horizon 2020	31/12/2022
FIRE	Forum for Innovation and Research in European Earth Observation	https://fire-forum.eu	Natassa Antoniou natassa.antoniou@ears.org	Horizon 2020	30/11/2022
Climateurope	European climate observations, modelling and services	https://www.climateurope.eu/	MET OFFICE	Horizon 2020	31/01/2021

7 Involvement of WPs in community engagement

Involving the climate services community is a shared effort that requires coordination within the Climateurope2 project. The community is critical for understanding standardisation needs and is therefore needed for providing information to key deliverables in, for example, WP1. Community members should experience coherence in the approach and activities. To achieve this, internal communication is needed about the stakeholder engagement every WP plans to do.

WP6 assists with creating connections between WPs 1-5 and the climate services community when this is needed. All WPs will have direct contacts with members of the climate services community as well, and more so as the project progresses. WP6 offers expertise and services for new and/or better interaction. To ensure a fluent communication process and to prevent user fatigue, WP6 has created an event calendar which is to be filled by all WPs. The calendar will provide information on all events planned by each WP to increase efficiency while avoiding overlap and keep the community engaged.

Some WPs already have stakeholder interaction planned in the work package descriptions, and some already mention WP6 as an assisting WP in those actions. These actions are listed under the events and channels sections above. During the course of the project, additional needs for community engagement will emerge in WPs 1-5 and WP6 will monitor these needs regularly.

7.1 Connecting WP6 tasks with tasks in other WPs

A discussion with WPs 1-5 is needed to define specific aims and targets. Coordinating and supporting efforts of WP6 for these WPs include:

- Surveys among WPs for collecting input for webinars, Webstivals and Festivals
- Guidelines and assistance with formulating stakeholder surveys, evaluations, and interviews
- Assistance with organising stakeholder meetings, e.g., what interaction methods can be used
- Guidelines for GDPR
- Guidelines for diversity and equality
- Guidelines for carbon friendly arrangements
- (Two-)Monthly WP management telcos with cross WP meetings

Task 7.1 is about Communication, dissemination and exploitation. The difference between tasks 6.1 and 7.1 is that 6.1 prioritises interaction (two way communication) rather than communication and dissemination, which tends to be one way. Task 6.1 targets a smaller group than 7.1, since the latter also includes potential users of climate services and the general public. The Climateurope2 network will be constituted of different types of stakeholders with different degrees of engagement. Some of them can be more passive, i.e. interested just in receiving information about project activities, while others can be really active and register in the Climateurope2 platform when it is developed. Active stakeholders can contribute to the discussions on the platform and during the events organised by the project. WP6 mainly aims at these active members of the climate services community during the runtime of the project.

Task 7.3 includes capacity building. In support of WP7, WP6 will identify what community engagement materials are needed to encourage community members to join the network and stay engaged. A flyer was already developed at the start of the project, in a cooperation between WP6, WP7 and other WPs (See Figure 6).

Climateurope2

SUPPORTING AND STANDARDISING CLIMATE SERVICES IN EUROPE AND BEYOND

Climateurope2 is a Horizon Europe Coordination and Support Action that will run from 2022-2027. The project aims to support and develop the community of climate services in Europe. It also aims to increase the uptake of climate services and their standardisation process. **Climate services** are information and knowledge that can help people and organizations deal with the impacts of climate variability and climate change.

WHY JOIN THE CLIMATEUROPE2 NETWORK?

Climateurope2 will support the development of future equitable and quality-assured climate services of greater value to society, which will provide trustworthy, user-relevant and usable information.

For that, we need to involve all the actors in the climate services value chain. **We will develop a network across Europe to improve the connection, engagement and promotion of European climate service activities.**

JOIN OUR NETWORK

In our network you will be able to:

- **Engage** with the community of climate services through the interactive Climateurope2 Platform
- **Participate in discussions** on the standardisation of climate services' components with the aim to reach consensus with the different actors involved
- **Have direct access to information** about good practices, recommendations, capacity-building materials, vocabularies and standardisation processes of for climate services
- **Be informed about activities** bringing the network together, including festivals, webstivals, a roadshow, a webinar series, business breakfasts and much more!

infoclimateurope2@bsc.es

@climateurope2

/company/climateurope2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101056933

climateurope2.eu

Figure 6. Flyer explaining why to join the Climateurope2 network.

Task 8.1 includes maintaining a connection with relevant European initiatives such as EOSC and several Horizon projects in Cluster 3, 4 and 5. WP8 will organize structural contacts with the project coordinators; WP6 can connect to these initiatives through WP8, for example, to involve them in a Webstival or webinar.

Task 8.2 is a Strategy for communication within the consortium. The difference between 6.1 and 8.2 is that 8.2 purely aims for the partners in the consortium, while 6.1 actively facilitates cooperation between the consortium and stakeholders outside the consortium. The strategy described here does include communication within the consortium about stakeholder interaction.

8 Methods to monitor progress of the network

The aim of the project is to expand the network beyond what was achieved in Climateurope, both in quantitative terms and in diversity. In order to achieve these goals, we need to monitor the progress and find out in what areas extra efforts are needed. In addition, we need to find out what methods and measures work, and if we need to try different alternatives for achieving diversity across the network as well as equity and inclusion regarding the participation of network members in the project activities. Diversity can refer to personal characteristics such as age and gender, but also to geographic diversity across Europe and diversity in types of stakeholders (e.g. public and private, different economic sectors). In future updates of the Climateurope2 engagement strategy, each method described will be considered and assessed according to its effectiveness. If necessary, initially established methods may be abandoned or adjusted, and new methods added.

The total number of community members is a Key Performance Indicator for WP6 (See Table 5 for the KPIs of WP6). The number of individuals participating in the network will be monitored. Next to this we will acquire data on the size of the organisations they are part of; assuming that the knowledge they acquire will impact their organisations and thus increases the impact of the Climateurope2 project.

Table 5. WP6 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

KPI #	KPI description	KPI target
6.1	Number of stakeholders in the managed community	>300 in total
6.2	Attendees at the events organised to support the community (Festivals, Webstivals, roadshow)	>500
6.3	Overall satisfaction with the event assessed through evaluation form	More than 3.5 on average
6.4	Attendees at user perspectives webinar series	>300
6.5	Attendees to business breakfasts	>50

A monitoring tool will be developed for tracking the network's diversity. Aspects to be monitored are regional gaps (e.g. in terms of EU Member States or European countries), gender balance, age (e.g. youth engagement), and gaps in sectors or organisation types. We will set benchmarks rather than targets, and we can go with the data-driven quota approach, e.g. the gender balance can be 40/60 in a community where there are realistically 40% of those who identify as female, and 60% of those who identify as male, in order to acquire a more realistic sample of the community. Another way to go would be the inclusion strategy, e.g. we can set the benchmark for involving certain regions, wherein we want to oversample e.g. Eastern Europe, since this region was less involved in Climateurope. The diversity guideline provides input for the monitoring.

Methods we can use to track progress are analysis of contact form interactions via the project website, feedback from stakeholders at events, surveys and interviews. Post-event surveys are planned after each of the events organised by Climateurope2. Progress will be reported in the updated versions of the Engagement Strategy (M21 and M33). Monitoring diversity may involve sensitive personal data, which should be collected, managed and stored considering the GDPR guidelines.

Annex: Task 6.1 in Grant Agreement

Task 6.1 Establish, monitor and develop the European climate service network [M1-M50] (CPN lead, REH, WR, CMCC, Ecologic, RHMZ, SMHI, BSC, MetOffice)

Building on Climateurope’s legacy and other activities (e.g. JPI-Climate/ERA4CS, C3S, CSP, GFCS, and the European Climate Pact), this task will **establish and monitor the Climateurope2 network**. The task will also **identify gaps in the diversity of the participants** of this European climate service network and develop a **strategy to improve the representation of different stakeholder typologies** from public and private sectors, reach a **greater inclusion from under-represented regions** (e.g. Eastern Europe) and **enhance the attainment of gender balance** across the network. A **concise live document describing the network status and including a Community Engagement Strategy will be available in M9 (D6.1)** and updated twice in the project lifetime to monitor the network evolution and engagement and adjust the strategy to reach low-represented and highly-relevant communities. This will include analysis of potential biases in the established community (e.g. gender and other biases). The data collected in WP6 will be analysed to understand the network dynamics and relevant results will be published for the benefit of the wider community including recommendations for the legacy and sustainability of the network beyond the project lifetime (D6.5).

Figure 7. Work package 6 deliverable legend

Table 6. WP6 Deliverables

Deliverable #	Deliverable title	Due month
D6.1	Community Engagement Strategy	M9
D6.2	First assessment of organised activities and first update to the community engagement strategy	M21
D6.3	Intermediate assessment of organised activities and second update to the community engagement strategy	M33
D6.4	Final assessment of organised activities and recommendations for future events	M46
D6.5	Recommendations for the future sustainability and improvement of the network and community, and the development of new forums based on lessons learnt	M50